

ROLE OF YOGA IN MAINTAINING GOOD PHYSICAL AND MENTAL HEALTH

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ABSTRACT: Yoga is very much concerned today. Yoga is the science of life and the art of living. Yoga arose in the age of the Vedas and Upanishads. It is India's oldest scientific, perfect spiritual discipline. Yoga is a method of training the mind and developing its power of subtle perceptions so that man may discover for himself the spiritual truths on which religion, beliefs and moral values finally rest. The yogic activities provide immense help in assisting an individual to seek his all round growth and development. Present world practice yoga for maintaining good health. Investigators, in this paper, try to explore the role of yoga in maintaining good physical and mental health.

KEY WORDS: Yoga, Vedas, Physical Education, Upanishads, Spiritual, Good Health,

I. INTRODUCTION

Physical education and yoga are interrelated. Yoga is one of the most ancient metaphysical sciences, which investigates the nature of soul and through its discipline, awakens the super conscious mind of the man which unites the moral being with the immortal supreme spirit. Yoga leads to balance and also provides both a philosophy and a religion. The real joy of life appears when we can unify nature and culture, wealth and poverty, movement and stillness, attachment and detachment. The yogic activities provide immense help in assisting an individual to seek his all round growth and development in all the personality dimensions including the union of his self with the Greater soul. Many still believe that yoga is a religion, but it's not, instead, it's a way of living who strives to have a healthy mind in a healthy body. A human is a mental, physical and spiritual being and yoga helps promote a balanced development of all the three. Other forms of physical exercises, such as aerobics, guarantee only physical well being. They

have very little to do with the development of the spiritual or planetary body. The exercises performed through yoga recharge the body with cosmic energy, which facilitates

□ Accomplishment of ideal equilibrium and harmony, □ Promotes self healing,, □ Takes out negative blocks from the mind and toxins from the body □ Increases personal power and self awareness, □ Helps in focusing and achieving concentration, which is particularly important for children, □ Lessens stress and tension in the physical body by activating the parasympathetic nervous system, The person performing this art feels rejuvenated, thus yoga bestows upon every individual the powers to control the body and mind.

II. METHODOLOGY

In this paper, the research was based on secondary data taken from different Books, research reports, journals and research papers.

III. OBJECTIVES

- To Know about the Yoga.
- To know about good health.
- To assess the Importance of Yoga for maintaining good physical health in present day's busy life.
- To find out the importance of Yoga in reducing Stress & anxiety to maintain Good Mental health.

YOGA:

The term —Yoga means union or merger. Yoga, as the spiritual goal, denotes the union of the Individual Soul with the Supreme Soul (God). As per Hindu Religious faith, this union or merger leading to Liberation or Emancipation is the supreme goal of all individuals. And Yoga as a tool helps the spirants attain their goals.

Yoga and its Importance in Our Daily Life

In practical terms, Yoga denotes functional harmony between the body and the mind. The harmony gained as a result of the practice of Yoga, leads to inexplicable joy, good health, long life, peace and happiness. Yoga has immense capabilities to develop the physical and mental

health. It cures diseases, including the dreaded ones. However, as a curative science, much of its potential still remains to be tapped. The first to write a compendium (compilation) on Yoga was Sage Patanjali who is believed to have lived in 200 B.C. or earlier. This work of Sage Patanjali, known as —Yoga Sutraḥ or —Yoga Darshanam is regarded as the most precise and scientific text ever written on Yoga. Sage Patanjali defines Yoga as Yogaschitta vrtti nirodahâ – Yoga is restraining the Mind-stuff from taking various forms. In other words, Yoga is the elimination of the modifications of the mind and making it one-pointed. Chittaâ (mind-stuff) means individual consciousness, which includes the conscious, the subconscious, and the unconscious states of mind. These three states of the individual mind are called Chittaâ. The waves of thought in the Chittaâ are called Vrttisâ. Nirodahâ means restraining or eliminating. So, restraining the modifications of the Chittaâm is the subject matter or the end goal of Yoga. Restraining the Chitta (mind-stuff) appears to be very simple. But, in practice, it is a very difficult task.

The aspirant will know the complexity and depth of the subject matter only while going through the verses, one by one, in all 196 verses, divided into 4 chapters. The work does not contain any techniques to help the beginners. This implies that the Yoga Sutraḥ are not meant for beginners and that a teacher is necessary to pursue the studies seriously. The beginning verse Atha Yoganusanamâ (Now, therefore, complete instructions on Yoga) itself is a clear indication to it. The word Athaâ (now, therefore) signifies that the student ought to have acquired adequate knowledge in Yoga before studying the Yoga Sutraḥ.

Types of Yoga: Four types of Yoga in India:

Basically there are four Yoga in India, viz., Karma Yoga, Bhakti Yoga, Raja Yoga and Jnana Yoga. Karma is suitable for people of active temperament. Bhakti Yoga is for people of devotional temperament. Raja Yoga, for men of mystic temperament and bold understanding and strong willpower. Bhakti Yoga is suitable for vast majority of persons as they are emotional. Jnana Yoga is suitable for a microscopic minority only. Ladies can realise God quickly as their hearts are filled with devotion, Prema and affection. But it is very difficult for them to get Vairagy. In Sanskrit "Ashta + anga" is Ashtanga. "Ashta" means Eight and "Anga" is limbs so it means Eight Limb path, ashtanga yoga is based on Yoga Philosophy of Patanjali. Yoga has its roots about 5000 years BC as described in Vedic Philosophy and Tantras. Patanjali, great sage

composed this path into a Darshan(Philosophy) in his Book Patanjali Yoga Sutra. In which he has formulated Yoga as a Eight Limbs or Eight Fold path.

Eight Limbs of Ashtanga Yoga are: □ Yama (Principles or moral code) , Ahimsa - A principle of non- violence Satya - A principle of Truthfulness Asteya - A principle of non stealing Brahmacharya - Continnence / Celibacy Aparigraha - A principle of non-hoarding or non possessiveness □ Niyama (Personal Disciplines) Shoucha – Purity Santosh – Contentment Tapa – Endurance Swadhyaya - Self study Eshwar Pranidhan – Dedication □ Asana (Yoga Positions or Yogic Postures) A stable and comfortable posture which helps attains mental equilibrium. □ Pranayama (Yogic Breathing) Extension and control of breath. □ Pratyahara (Withdrawal of Senses) A mental preparation to increase the power of mind. □ Dharana (Concentration on Object) Concentration of mind on one object and its field. □ Dhyana (Meditation) With drawing mind from all external objects and Focusing it on one point and meditating on it. □ Samadhi (Salvation) State of super bliss, joy and merging individual consciousness in to universal consciousness. Union between Jivatman and Paramatman. Union of Shiva and Shakti in Sahasrar Chakra (the top of the head). Realizing the Bramhan (pure consciousness) or Realization of God is the ultimate achievement of Human Birth.

Yoga in the ancient period:

The Beginning: About 5,000 years ago, yoga was invented. We think this happened in the Indus Valley, on a sunny Tuesday afternoon. We know this because we've uncovered stone carvings that show people sitting in meditative-looking positions. It's worth noting that this is well before Hinduism came into being. Also of interest, ancient Egyptian images from over 5,000 years ago show some pretty good tree-poses, among other things. Concluding things about ancient times can get a little wobbly, especially without context. Vedic Period: Between 3,500 and 2,500 years ago the Vedas were written, which formed the basis for Hinduism. Yogis at this time were often solitary types, living in forests. Their interests aimed at enduring physical hardship by sharpening their minds.

Pre-Classical Yoga: About 2,500 years ago, the Upanishads were written. The Bhagavad Gita is left as the oldest known yoga scripture, dating to 500 BCE. Yoga practice seems to soften a bit, becoming more meditative and less reclusive.

Classical: Patanjali's Yoga Sutras form the defining text here, outlining the Eightfold Path of yoga:

What to do and not do, how to relate with ourselves and others, how to sit, breathe, withdraw, focus, concentrate, meditate, and of course, enlighten. It's worth noting there is only a single mention of physical activity here, as preparation for proper sitting. Modern day's relevance: Today, millions of people across the world are following yoga either in the form of one particular asana or a combination taught by a Yogi or guru. Some books even refer to particular asana depending upon the medical requirement. Modern yogis claims that yogic exercises cure various diseases like obesity, diabetics, dislocation of disc, respiratory problems, arthritis of various types and various spine problems, high blood pressure besides stress and even cholesterol problems and heart diseases. Yoga guru Swami Ramdev and many of his cults are making yoga more popular all over the world by demonstrating modern physical exercise of yoga.

Yoga in India: The 'Upanishads' and 'Puranas' composed by Indian Aryans in the later Vedic and post-Vedic period contain references to yoga. Patanjali wrote 'Y ga Sutra', about two thousand Years ago. 'Yoga Sutra' is the most important basic text on Yoga. Swami Ramdev, a new-age yoga guru is dominating Indian viewers with both his performances of yoga asanas and his candid comments against corruption. Swami Ramdev, who hosts a television show with 30 million viewers across the country, owns a peace island in Scotland. Swami Ramdev has ushered in a hope for people suffering from different kinds of ailments, even the incurable ones. Thousands of people in Europe and USA have attended his Yogic exercises. In India, millions in urban and rural areas watch the Yoga exercise on TV and listen intently to his discourses.

Spirit of Yoga:

The true spirit of Yoga revolves around uplifting the life force or 'Kundalini' at the base of the spine. It strives to accomplish this through a series of mental and physical exercises. At the physical level, the methods consist several yoga postures or 'asanas' that strives to keep the body healthy. The mental techniques include breathing techniques or 'pranayama' and

meditation or 'dhyana' to discipline the mind. Ultimately, yoga aims to help the person to rise above the self and attain enlightenment.

GOOD HEALTH:

Good health is a reflection of body, mind and spirit. Through integration of moderate functional exercise, meditation and awareness, balanced nutrition, morality and peace-loving relationships (with family, at the workplace and with friends), the absence of disease can be attained. Health is a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity. Health is precisely, that condition in which human being has full sensitivity and in which all his faculties are operating fully. To tively work towards this condition is to cure illness and to develop maximum health. Yoga is both a philosophy and a living religion, believes that the body is so important and trains it so strictly. Without health we can neither practice meditation nor attain enlightenment. For total health one should seek the truth by skepticism. The body mind system possesses the innate power of recovering health and the yogic method of curing human ills aims at stimulating it. Prominent health specialist Ben Jonson said, "O, health! health! the blessing of rich! the riches ofthe poor! Who can buy thee at too dear a rate, since there is no enjoying the world without thee! Preksha (means to see inside with full concentration) may appear to mean different things to different people because it contributes to increase physical, nervous as well as spiritual energies. As per prominent Jainacharya Acharya Mahaprajna inventor of Preksha Dhyana Yoga total health consists of physical, mental, emotional and spiritual health. On physical level, it helps each bodily cell to revitalize itself; it facilitates digestion, it makes inspiration more efficient and improves circulation and quality of blood. On mental level it proves to be an applied method to train the mind to concentrate; it offers way to treat serious psychosomatic illness without drugs; it is an efficient tool for ending addictions and other bad habits; it

Yoga and its Importance in Our Daily Life

The data reveals to one the mysteries of his mind by the realization and real experience of the inner consciousness which includes the subconscious and the unconscious. On the emotional level, the strengthening of conscious reasoning controls reactions to environmental conditions, situations and behaviour of others; harmonization of the functioning of nervous and endocrine

system results in control and ultimate eradication of psychological distortions. On spiritual level, regulation and transformation of blood chemistry through proper synthetization of neuro endocrinal secretions, dispassionate internal vibrations leads one to attain the power to control the mind and to become free from the effect of external forces compelling one to lose to equanimity.

Jainacharya Acharya Mahaprajna inventor of Preksha Dhyan Yoga inspires for maintenance of total health: □ For maintenance of physical health one should always walk in morning fresh air and should observe Asans and Pranayama. □ For maintenance of mental health one should get rid of worries and should deep dive in meditation and kayotsarga. □ For achieving emotional health one should think positive and should always live in present and not in past or future.

Sound health and peaceful mind are a must for man to enjoy the material world. In order to achieve this purpose of birth one has to maintain harmony between body and life force, life force and mind, between individuals and society and between natures and will. Practicing appropriate exercises of body and mind and a virtuous way of living to maintain the harmonies described above constitute yoga. Thus Karma Yoga is a system of life utilizing the full Potential of the body and mind with understanding and awareness for a happy, prosperous and peaceful life. All experiences in life are enjoyed only by the mind. Mind is the peripheral stage of consciousness. In the infinite state, the consciousness itself is the truth. As a man is endowed with the sixth sense which inherits the purpose of the realization of self, in time he should realize the self, which is consciousness. By realizing consciousness man can live with satisfaction, harmony and peace. Realization of consciousness is the only one perfect and higher knowledge by which one can know everything in the universe. The mind is nothing but the extended and perceptual activity of the consciousness. One should do every action, whether thought, word or deed, with a perspective awareness not to inflict pain to self or others, at present or in future, to the body or mind. Physical and mental health is important for a happy and successful life. One has to maintain these with due care,

Yoga and Its Importance in Our Daily Life:

Leading a creative life so as to be a useful member of the society throughout the span of one's life is the chief aim and thrust of karma Yoga.

Role of Yoga Maintaining Good Health:

Weight loss, a strong and flexible body, glowing beautiful skin, peaceful mind, and good health whatever you may be looking for, yoga has it on offer. However, very often, yoga is only partially understood as being limited to asanas (yoga poses). As such, its benefits are only perceived to be at the body level and we fail to realize the immense benefits yoga offers in uniting the body, mind and breath. When you are in harmony, the journey through life is calmer, happier and more fulfilling. With all this and much more to offer, the benefits of yoga are felt in a profound yet subtle manner.

Here, we look at the important benefits of yoga practice.

☐ **All-round fitness:** You are truly healthy when you are not just physically fit but also mentally and emotionally balanced. As Sri Sri Ravi Shankarji puts it, —Health is not a mere absence of disease. It is a dynamic expression of life – in terms of how joyful, loving and enthusiastic you are. This is where yoga helps: postures, pranayama (breathing techniques) and meditation are a holistic fitness package.

☐ **Weight loss.** What many want! Yoga benefits here too. Sun Salutations and Kapal Bhati pranayama are some ways to help lose weight with yoga. Moreover, with regular practice of yoga, we tend to become more sensitive to the kind of food our body asks for and when. This can also help keep a check on weight.

☐ **Stress relief.** A few minutes of yoga during the day can be a great way to get rid of stress that accumulates daily - in both the body and mind. Yoga postures, pranayama and meditation are effective techniques to release stress.

☐ **Inner peace.** We all love to visit peaceful, serene spots, rich in natural beauty. Little do we realize that peace can be found right within us and we can take a mini-vacation to experience this

any time of the day! Benefit from a small holiday every day with yoga and meditation. Yoga is also one of the best ways to calm a disturbed mind.

□ **Improved immunity.** Our system is a seamless blend of the body, mind and spirit. An irregularity in the body affects the mind and similarly unpleasantness or restlessness in the mind can manifest as an ailment in the body. Yoga poses massage organs and strengthens muscles; breathing techniques and meditation release stress and improve immunity.

□ **Living with greater awareness.** The mind is constantly involved in activity – swinging from the past to the future – but never staying in the present. By simply being aware of this tendency of the mind, we can actually save ourselves from getting stressed or worked up and relax the mind. Yoga and pranayama help create that awareness and bring the mind back to the present moment, where it can stay happy and focused.

□ **Better relationships.** Yoga can even help improve your relationship with your spouse, parents, friends or loved ones! A mind that is relaxed, happy and contented is better able to deal with sensitive relationship matters. Yoga and meditation work on keeping the mind happy and peaceful; benefit from the strengthened special bond you share with people close to you.

□ **Increased energy.** Do you feel completely drained out by the end of the day? Shuttling between multiple tasks through the day can sometimes be quite exhausting. A few minutes of yoga everyday provides the secret to feeling fresh and energetic even after a long day. A 10-minute online guided meditation benefits you immensely, leaving you refreshed and recharged in the middle of a hectic day.

□ **Better flexibility & posture.** You only need to include yoga in your daily routine to benefit from a body that is strong, supple and flexible. Regular yoga practice stretches and tones the body muscles and also makes them strong. It also helps improve your body posture when you stand, sit, sleep or walk. This would, in turn, help relieve you of body pain due to incorrect posture.

□ **Better intuition.** Yoga and meditation have the power to improve your intuitive ability so that you effortlessly realize what needs to be done, when and how, to yield positive results. It works. You only need to experience it yourself.

□ **Powerful lunge.** Yoga activities specially concerned with pranayam help in the promotion and increase in strength and stamina of our lunge power in terms of their expansion and contraction enabling us to inhale maximum amount of oxygen in our body for the purification of our blood besides helping in the proper circulation of the purified blood in all corners of our body.

□ **Improve respiratory power.** Yoga help us in regulating the respiration activities of our body adding efficiency to our respiratory power including increase in its amplitude stability and smoothness and decrease in the respiratory rate.

□ **Healthy muscles .**These provide valuable help in the proper functioning and control over the movement of our muscles including the spinal cord. As a result we are able to maintain proper posture of our body including proper erectness of our spinal cord. These also contribute in the desired increase in our muscular strength besides maintaining the needed muscular flexibility and smoothness resulting in the energetic youthfulness considerably for a quite longer period of our life.

□ **Purify body.** These help us in the tasks of the cleanliness and purification of the inner organs and systems of our body including the purification of our blood and its pathways, cleanliness of the respiratory and digestive systems and proper let out and excretion of the unwanted foreign material from our body .

□ **Healthy body.** Yoga activities not only prove as strong deterrent for the prevention of the various ailments and diseases but also provide valuable solutions for their proper cure and treatment. For example it has been a matter of wide experience that Yogic activities provide substantial cure and treatment in the cases of arthritis, back pain, and osteoporosis, high and low blood pressure, asthma, diabetes and epilepsy, headaches, heart disease and multiple sclerosis etc.

□ **Powerful mind.** It is well said that there lies a healthy mind in a healthy body maintained through yogic activities. One can enjoy good mental health with a sound physical health obtained through yogic activities. Yogic activities help in equipping one properly and sufficiently with all the essential cognitive and mentalabilities and capacities for reaching the top of his intellectual and mental development. Yogic Asans, pranayam and practice of Dhyan, Dharana and samadhi can help an individual to have sufficient gains in terms of the improvement in his power of

concentration, memorization, attention, learning efficiency, steadiness, and mind body neuro connection etc.

□ **Strong sense organs.** Yogic activities help in making one's sense organs healthy, strong and effectively functioning. In turn it helps the individual to have a sizable increase in their reception ability, somatic and kinesthetic awareness and sensitivity for acquiring new knowledge and experiences through the use of their sense organs.

□ **Control over mind.** Yog sadhna provides the desired ability and strength for exercising desirable control over his senses, emotions and gratification of desires and fluctuations of the mind. Sustaining of attention and concentration acquired through such control and restraint then may provide a substantial ground of the development of intellectual powers. It can be given a further higher impetus by resorting to the practice of yogic activities like Dharna, Dhyan and Samadhi.

□ **Internal purification.** Yog sadhna helps not only to have purification and cleanliness of the internal organs and systems of our body but it also pays a lot of consideration for the purification of our inner self i.e. purification of our thoughts and feelings.

□ **Self development.** Yogic activities help the individual to imbibe the spirit of self awareness, confidence in one's abilities and strengths, self discipline and intrinsic motivation, self-acceptance and self actualization etc for seeking his maximum self development and enhancement.

□ **Reduced Conflict.** Yoga may also help students get along better with one another, which fosters a more positive learning environment. A school in Milwaukee instituted a yoga program consisting of two classes per week for students in kindergarten through 8th grade. The classes emphasized respectful behaviour as well as yogic breathing and movement practices. After a year, the school's number of disruptive "incidents" decreased by more than half. Yoga may teach students to better manage their emotions and reactions as well as to respect the feelings and emotions of others.

- **Healthy mind.** Yogic activities help to free from any unusual anxiety, depression and fluctuation of mood or temperament. Such state of one's mind may help him much in excelling in terms of his intellectual growth and wisdom.
- **Improved Concentration.** Yoga offers time for the body and mind to relax from the rigors of learning. This may help students be better at applying themselves when studying or learning in a classroom. Medical students who practiced yoga for just one month reported better sleep and improved concentration during their studies as a result in a study published in a 2013 issue of the "Indian Journal of Community Medicine." Yoga, especially breathing techniques, can also increase concentration and academic performance in students struggling academically, concluded a 2012 study published by the International Society for Scientific Interdisciplinary Yoga Research.
- **Powerful boosts.** Aside from the uplifting spiritual values, the act of meditation can actually boost your confidence. The process works by releasing tension from you mind so you can feel confident about your physical body. Without any forms of anxiety, you are able to establish an internal connection with yourself. This is consequently reflected in your perception of others and will help to better your relationships by improving compassion and awareness.

CONCLUSION

A person practicing yoga can control his/her mind, body and soul to a great extent. It brings together mental and physical disciplines to achieve a peaceful mind and body and helps in managing stress and anxiety and keep you relaxed. It also helps in enhancing muscle strength, flexibility and body tone and improves respiration, energy and vitality. You might feel that practicing yoga is just stretching, but it can do much more for your body, from the way you feel, look and move. This fact itself speaks volumes about the popularity of Yoga in the modern day world. This event has united the world on a common platform. Along with yoga, meditation also plays an important role in developing the inner self in our daily life; it can be extremely helpful in eliminating several physical as well as psychological problems. Yoga is a traditional method of meditation developed by the saints of ancient India. They practiced yoga as an effective method of controlling their mind and bodily activities. When the body is physically healthy, the mind is clear, focused and stress is under control. This gives the space to connect with loved

ones and maintain socially healthy relationships. When you are healthy you are in touch with your inner Self, with others and your surroundings on a much deeper level, which adds to your spiritual health. All these facets justify why we need an International Yoga Day celebration to prepare the mankind face the modern day challenges and stress in a healthy way.

Yoga is a continuous process. So keep practicing! The deeper you move into your yoga practice, the more profound are its benefits. Yoga practice helps develop the body and mind bringing a lot of health benefits yet is not a substitute for medicine. It is important to learn and practice yoga postures under the supervision of a trained Yoga teacher.

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